

Agronomic characteristics

Off-season growing of photoperiod-sensitive rices in Los Baños at 13°40'N

R. Herrera and D. HilleRisIambers, Plant Breeding Department, IRRI

Photoperiod-sensitive rices, often planted late in the wet season by farmers and researchers, grow well into the dry season.

Farmers in Bangladesh grow a photoperiod-sensitive transplanted crop of Nizersail after aus (early wet season) rices. Photoperiod sensitivity speeds flowering, allowing the transplanted crop to flower before harmful cold temperatures occur late in the season.

Plant breeders in Barisal, Bangladesh, plant varieties near the end of the year to help assess flowering behavior: early flowering indicates photoperiod sensitivity. Breeders at IRRI and elsewhere plant photoperiod-sensitive and insensitive progenitors twice annually to facilitate single and double crosses.

When a hybridization block is planted at bimonthly intervals in the slowly increasing day lengths during the off season, day length a few weeks after seeding determines whether a photoperiod-sensitive variety will flower or not (Table 1). With every successive planting date, more photoperiod-sensitive entries fail to flower.

Experience from two dry seasons is summarized in Table 2. These data may be useful for off-season seed increases. Some extrapolation from an entry in Table 2 to a similar variety from the same region and cultural type should be possible. Note that early failures to flower often refer to Sri Lankan and South Indian varieties. □

Table 1. Factors affecting flowering behavior of photoperiod-sensitive rices when planted in the increasing day lengths of the off season.

Factor	Effect
Planting date (environmental)	A late date may postpone flowering altogether.
Basic vegetative phase (BVP) (genotypic)	A long BVP has an effect similar to that of delayed planting date.
Cold temperature (environmental)	Cold temperatures lengthen BVP and delay or postpone flowering.
Nutrition (environmental)	Low nutritional status lengthens BVP and delays or postpones flowering.
Critical day length (genotypic)	Longer critical day lengths enable plants to continue to flower longer into the dry season.

Table 2. Earliest off-season planting dates at which hybridization block entries of 1981-82 and 1982-83 failed to flower.

Seeding date ^a	1981-82	1982-83
6 Jan (1981-82)	ASD5 BKNFR76046-70-2-5-3 GEB 24	Hondarawala Nam Sagui 19 PTB 18
21 Jan (1981-82)	BKN6721-5-7-4 BKN7022-6-4 Chamara CR1030 FR43B IR1820-52-2-4-1 IR11288-BB-69-1 IR13358-85-1-3	IR13365-253-3-2 IR5533-13-1-1 IR11288-B-B-118-1 Khao Dawk Mali 105 MTU 7029 Niaw San Pahtong Patnai 23 Peta
7 Dec (1981-82)	Molaga Samba	
22 Dec (1981-82)	Balaratawee Hathili PTB 21 Raminad Str. 3	
16 Jan (1982-83)	BR118-3B-17 BR10 CN540 CR 1009 IR5 IR43	IR17494-32-3-1-1-3 IR3273-289-2-1473 IR4547-4-1-2 Pelita I/1 SPR7210-1-10-2-1 UBN 6721-11-1-6
1 Dec (1982-83)	No record of failure to flower	
16 Dec (1982-83)	BKNFR 76026-3-2-1-2 SPR7411-7-2-1 TOX896-R-R-R-102 RD19	
31 Dec (1982-83)		

^a Days after transplanting = days after seeding + 20.

IR50 – an early-maturing, fine-grained rice for kar season

W. Manuel, K. Ganesan, and S. Chockalingam, Paddy Experiment Station (PES), Ambasamudram 627401, Tamil Nadu, India

IR50, a semidwarf rice variety with long, slender white grains and high tillering potential, was released for general cultiva-

Comparative performance of IR50 at Ambasamudram, Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)			Total duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles (no./hill)	Panicle wt (g)
	1981	1982	Mean				
IR50	6.2	5.7	6.0	110	78	10	1.1
ADT31	6.5	6.0	6.2	110	94	8	1.5
TKM9	6.5	5.3	5.9	109	88	9	1.6
IET4786	6.4	5.2	5.8	109	91	9	1.0
m + σ	6.4	—	—	—	—	—	—
CD (P = 0.05)		0.55	—	—	—	—	—